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Oxidations with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV). Part I: Milligram Determination of Polycyclic Hydrocarbons

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THE small scale determination of hydrocarbon function has always attracted organic analytical chemists because of the slow reactivity of the function and the lack of a general procedure. Quick and direct methods have been given for the small scale determination of cyclic hydrocarbons¹⁻³. Recently the spectrophotometric⁴⁻⁶, gas chromatographic⁷ and fluorescence spectrum techniques⁸ have been applied for detection and determination of polycyclic hydrocarbons. Marletta⁹ has reviewed in detail the recent developments in the determination of aromatic polynuclear hydrocarbons.

Taking advantage of the oxidising capacity of ammonium hexanitratocerate (iv) in nitric acid medium, a quick, precise and accurate (within 0.3-0.85% error) method has been developed for the milligram determination of polycyclic hydrocarbons at room temperature (25°) within five minutes reaction time.

Experimental

Reagent :

0.1 M Ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution was prepared in 0.5 M nitric acid solution. 0.025 M aqueous ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and 1M sulfuric acid solution were prepared from reagent grade chemicals. 0.001 M aqueous ferroin solution was used as indicator.

Sample solution

40-50 mg. of the hydrocarbon was dissolved in glacial acetic acid in a 100 ml measuring flask. All the hydrocarbons were either recrystallised from the proper solvent till a constant melting point is obtained or procured in the pure form.

Procedure :

Aliquots containing 1-5 mg of the sample were taken in a 100 ml. conical flask and 5 ml. of 0.1 M Ce(IV) solution was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for five minutes at room temperature (25°). The reaction was quenched by adding 10 ml 1M sulfuric acid and the content shaken for a minute. The unreacted Ce(IV) was titrated against standard Fe(II) using ferroin indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions using all other reagents except for the sample. The recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the readings of Fe(II) for blank and the actual estimation.

$$\frac{\text{mg of hydrocarbon}}{\text{ml of 0.025 M Fe(ii) Soln} \times \text{Mol wt. of Hydrocarbon}} = \text{Molarity}$$

Results

Results obtained with the recommended procedure are given in the table. The effect of concentration of Ce(IV), varying amounts of hydrocarbon sample, reaction time and temperature was also studied for all the hydrocarbons. On the basis of stoichiometry and the identification of final oxidation products, it is established that all the hydrocarbons get oxidised to corresponding quinones.

The presence of phenols, amines, alcohols and aldehydes interfere in the estimation. However the oxidation of benzene is not possible with the recommended procedure.

TABLE : DETERMINATION OF POLYCYCLIC HYDROCARBONS WITH Ce(IV).

Compound	Amount taken (mg)	Amount recovered (mg)	Molarity	Deviation %
Naphthalene	1.0100	1.0140	6	+0.39
	3.0300	3.0409	-	+0.36
	5.0500	5.0662	-	+0.32
Anthracene	1.0600	1.0680	6	+0.75
	3.1800	3.1978	-	+0.56
	5.3000	5.3196	-	+0.37
Phenanthrene	1.2800	1.2876	6	+0.59
	3.8400	3.8584	-	+0.48
	5.1200	5.1379	-	+0.35
Acenaphthene	1.3400	1.3486	8	+0.64
	2.6800	2.6952	-	+0.57
	4.0200	4.0332	-	+0.33
Diphenyl	1.6200	1.6284	6	+0.51
	3.2400	3.2552	-	+0.47
	4.8600	4.8740	-	+0.29

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Chemical Constituents of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel¹

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TERPENES, sterols and flavonoids are known to occur in various species of *Eupatorium*; a common genus of the family Asteraceae (Compositae). Recently we reported the occurrence of a new triterpene epoxy lupeol², lupeol, β -amyrin and a flavone salvigenin³ from *Eupatorium odoratum*^{2,3} and eupacannol, a novel pentacyclic triterpene alcohol with a rearranged ursane skeleton from *Eupatorium cannabinum*⁴, both species being collected from Darjeeling. In continuation of our studies on Indian *Eupatorium* species we undertook the chemical investigation of an Indian variety of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel collected from Shillong in the Sub-Himalayan region of north-east India. Earlier workers reported chromenes from the Australian⁵ as well as Jamaican⁶ variety of the same plant. The present study has revealed the occurrence of taraxasteryl palmitate [urs-20(30)-en-3- β -ol-hexadecanoate: second natural occurrence] as the major product (0.09%) along with taraxasterol (0.01%), stigmasterol (0.02%) and two uncharacterised compounds — an unsaturated liquid hydrocarbon (0.04%) and a microcrystalline solid fatty alcohol (0.02%), m.p. 84-86°.

The light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the whole plant of *E. riparium* was chromatographed over silica gel, using solvents of increasing polarity.

Evaporation of the light petroleum eluted fraction furnished an oily residue (two distinct spots in TLC) which could be resolved into a colourless liquid *L* (yield 0.04%) and a crystalline compound *I* (yield 0.09%) upon repeated chromatographies over silica gel.

Compound *I* crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless needles, m.p. 102-03°, $[\alpha]_D +70^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.77); analysed for C₄₆H₈₀O₂ (M⁺ 664) and showed positive TNM colouration; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1722 cm⁻¹ (CO), 1633 (C=C), 863 (=CH₂ out-of-plane bending); PMR (60 MHz, CDCl₃) (δ) 2.27 (2H ill-defined *t*, *J* ~ 6Hz, CH₂CH₂COOR), 4.60 (2H, *m*, C=CH₂), 4.45 (1H, *m*, HCOCOR, the low field component buried under the C=CH₂ signal). From the above IR and PMR data *I* was suggested to be an ester. Saponification of *I* by treatment with 5% KOH solution in tetrahydrofuran-methanol(1:1) at room temperature, followed by usual work up, furnished an acid *A* and a triterpene alcohol *II*. The acid *A*, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, had m.p. 64°, C₁₆H₃₂O₂ (M⁺256); $[\alpha]_D \pm \theta^\circ$; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1690 cm⁻¹ (CO); weak absorption at 1375 cm⁻¹ indicates minimum substitution⁷; PMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) (δ) 2.29 (2H, *t*, *J* = 7Hz, RCH₂CH₂COOH), a broad singlet at δ 1.26 is assignable to protons of (CH₂)_{*n*} indicating the presence of a methylene chain. *A* was identified to be palmitic acid by its mass spectrometry⁸ showing M - 43 peak (expulsion of C₂, C₃, C₄ and 1H) and other characteristic peaks at *m/e* (M - 43 - 14*n*) and *m/e* (41 + 14*n*) where *n* = 0, 1, 2, 3... with the decrease of relative intensities as *n* increases, a characteristic of straight chain fatty acid. It was further confirmed by comparison of the GLC curve of its methyl ester (obtained by methylation of *A* with BF₃ in methanol) with that of an authentic sample of methyl palmitate.

The alcohol *II*, showing positive Liebermann-Burchardt colouration for triterpenes, crystallised from light petroleum-benzene (1:1) as colourless needles, m.p. 218-19°, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺426), $[\alpha]_D +91^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.76); ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3380 cm⁻¹ (OH), 1655 (C=C), 870 (=CH₂ out-of-plane bending); positive TNM colouration: PMR (60 MHz, CHCl₃) (δ) 0.76, 0.86, 0.90, 0.97, 1.03 and 1.09 (21H, seven methyls on saturated carbons), 4.60 (2H, *m*, C=CH₂), 3.22 (1H, ill-defined *q*, *J*_{ax-ax} ~ 9Hz, *J*_{ax-eq} ~ 5Hz, CHOH (axial). *II* formed an acetate *III*, m.p. 243-44°, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺468); $[\alpha]_D +107^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.67); Sarett oxidation of *II* with CrO₃/Py afforded *IV*, m.p. 180-81°. $[\alpha]_D +127^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.69): All these data and the mass fragmentation pattern⁹ of *II* (important ion peaks at *m/e* 411, 408, 357, 344, 315,